

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PROBLEM OF SOCIAL STEREOTYPES IN THE LEBANESE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

The current research sheds light on the teachers' knowledge and awareness of emotional intelligence and social emotional learning in schools in Lebanon. It highlights the benefits of social emotional learning programs in terms of creating equity in schools, nurturing the spirit of self-awareness, offering learners emotion regulation tools and the capability to build healthy long-lasting relationships based on empathy. The research was carried out in Lebanon throughout the year 2023 through focus groups, one to one meeting and a google form was used to survey the 104 participants. The teachers were from various governates in Lebanon, they taught different age groups, different cycles and across different subject areas. The research investigated emotions intelligence through skills such as self-awareness, empathy, emotion regulation and reading emotions in others in parallel with social stereotypes such as related to gender or profession. It offers recommendations and guidelines for school teachers, principals and policy makers to support initiating and maintaining such programs that would aim to introduce social emotional learning effectively inside classrooms and schools.

Keywords: Social stereotypes, mental health, emotional intelligence, identity, gender, school, teacher training, educational system.

The world pre and post Covid 19 pandemic won't be the same. People around the world fought the challenge in different ways, some with perseverance and survival mode, while others in hopelessness and demotivation. The United Nation has set 17 sustainable development goals to make the world a better place in the coming decade, until 2030. It placed high importance on improving the quality of current lives of societies and communities, whether through various approaches such as: removing poverty and eliminating hunger, offering health services, clean water and better life on land and in seas, and offering equal chances to all underprivileged members of the society. It placed a great importance on the quality of education, hand in hand with eradicating inequalities between genders in such a way that all societies can offer better quality of life to their members and make the world really a better place. Stereotypes are one of the social problems that may come to surface when investigating lives inside communities and relations among members. Oxford English dictionary defines a stereotype as "widely held, but fixed and oversimplified image or idea of a particular type of person or thing". Stereotypes can be generalizations about racial groups, political groups, genders, demographic groups, activities or even subgroups among broad populations.

To date, the evidence overwhelmingly suggests that stereotypes influence the manner in which information is sought, perceived, remembered, and judged [5]. When we talk about stereotypes, it is the common belief that categorizes people, in exaggerated matters

that may also not be true. This categorization that identifies people based on physical, social or cultural characteristics assumes that all people in a given category or subgroup will manifest all these given traits. Stereotyping always focuses on differences and offers extra edge to a group of people as if giving less rights to another [7]. When people endorse stereotypes, it leads to prejudice and discrimination towards members of minority groups. Frederic Bartlett (1932) examined what happened to information as it was repeatedly passed from person to person down a chain of individuals in a lab (a method akin to the children's game often called 'telephone' or 'Chinese whispers') [2]. Schools represent a model of community; it is a miniature version of a group of people living together with different ages and backgrounds, being ruled by a set of rules, policies and procedures. The same stereotypes can be examined on the school grounds and inside classrooms. This current study examined the members of the pedagogical institutions in the Armenian community in Lebanon. It shed light on the levels of stereotype present knowledge, their awareness, and factors of stereotypes, in education and pedagogical institutions.

Schools in general, and Armenian schools in specific, were founded in Lebanon with a common goal to transfer knowledge and experience, history and legacy, pass on values, and prepare the youth for the future with core values that are important to the Armenian nation and the identity of every Armenian. The Armenian community in Lebanon, in its turn, established social pedagogical organizations that represented the mission

of the founders and are still working to transmit knowledge and experience to the new generations. Social stereotypes were present in the lives of the first Armenians who reached the lands of Lebanon before a century or more. These stereotypes continue to affect lives of Armenians, still in the 21st century. In Lebanon Armenians are sometimes accepted as equal nationals in the country, whereas in other cases they are groups that support each other and choose the Armenian school, choose the Armenian products and services and simply sometimes choose the option where the Armenian touch is present. The mission and the vision of the Armenian parties and organizations in Lebanon may differ, yet they all have similar mission, improving the lives of the Armenians in the community, preparing citizens who serve the motherland as well as the nation they are born in. An interview with five Armenian school principals set the basis for some common stereotypes observed inside schools in Lebanon. Racial, gender and religious stereotypes are the most discriminating and harmful discrimination and even violence may result in frequent cases in the society. These stereotypes are yielded and clear continuous misconceptions about inequality among members and that results in segregation inside organizations. Stereotypes that are most visual in these schools are the groupings between Armenian and Non-Armenian students in these schools. Gender stereotypes are seen most frequently inside communities and especially inside schools. These principals specified the observed gender inequality in schools that is harming the future or so many young girls, due to unclear guidelines on how to combat gender inequalities in education between pedagogical staff, whether teachers or students. Stereotypes are mostly simple and superficial overgeneralizations in terms of cultural stereotypes: people from this specific area are lazy, individuals from villages are warm and welcoming to different social stereotypes in terms of specific group characteristics, economic class, age, skills, etc. Reasons may change, yet according to these principals, stereotypes give rise to create an unwelcoming atmosphere for some groups and give ownership of school facilities or specific "right" to some chosen, privileged groups. While stereotypes are rarely correct and certainly not always accurate, they are not always negative. In fact, some cast a positive light on a certain group or type of people. However, they are still overgeneralizations and ultimately not helpful because individuals and groups cannot be limited to a few stereotypical traits. Stereotypes therefore in teaching are the fixed images or ideas, whether behavioral, cognitive or affective criterions, to which a teacher views the self or is seen by others since they are in the professional educational activities. The same definition applies to stereotypes to learners. It is how different learners see themselves and others because they belong to a specific group and thus are placed in a specific criterion. When the question "what are some stereotypes related to teachers and learners" was asked to 50 teachers in Armenian schools in Lebanon, here are few answers from educators. The different members of the educational system have different set definitions, for example, in relation to teachers "teachers are mainly females", "teachers are talkative", "female teachers are emotionally more intelligent than male teachers." "Males manage stress better than females" When the questions in relation to learners were gathered some were "boys are

better in math", "boys don't cry" or "girls choose humanities and linguistic majors while boys choose scientific". In these educational institutions the clients, the students and their parents, the employees, teachers, principal and administration and the owners, such as board members, national parties or church entities organize the work and the relationship based on their internal bylaws [6]. Group dynamics and behavior are important points to examine to better understand the relationships and the expression of stereotypes between staff members. Commitment and compliance with group norms builds positive relationships among members and creates a common vision essential for the success of the institutions. Organizations that are built on the culture of globalization, accepting cross cultural differences and demographic diversities, minimizes intergroup conflicts. Intergroup interactions are present in every moment of life especially in schools where the main focus on work is on human-human relationships. The quality of relationships between members depends on the minimal conflicts present. The personal characteristics and intergroup relationships need to be examined in order to understand groups inside organizations. Individuals define and label themselves based on which groups they belong to and what are accepted behaviors as well as reward punishment systems placed. Common shared goal setting of individuals in team format allows individuals to accept the other based on the spirit of the organizations and encourages group work. When organizations focus on the importance of groups among the institutions and the quality of relationships, workload performance increases, creativity and open communication is channeled. Effective decision-making opportunities are offered to all teams, and all team members, allowing individuals to have higher job satisfaction and reduced problems.

Individuals contribute to group wellness and the group's progress is reflected in the organization. This mood is translated in the relationships and conflicts among members whether in terms of constant competitiveness or cooperation. When organizations are aware of individual characteristics and group dynamics, using correct methods and techniques, effective communication, collaboration, job satisfaction and motivation is created [6]. The environment that encourages acceptance, minimizes conflicts and between groups stereotypes. These organizations that invest in the individual and the team profile, gain improvement in the quality of relationships. Gender biased workforce catches attention in terms of equal pays, equal opportunities and the debate continues, yet in educational institutions, stereotypes impair professional performance of educators and academic performance of learners. When stereotypes remain unattended, they alter the potential and chance of educators and female learners at schools. Educational psychology can be the area to investigate which kind of policies should be implemented to alleviate the effects of gender stereotypes and in general stereotypes, to yield fair and just venues for all learners to feel safe, develop, grow and learn and reach to their maximum potential [3]. Gender stereotypes affect learners' classroom experiences, academic performance and even subject choice. The assumptions learners make, consciously or unconsciously, affect their future forever, whether boys or girls. Unconscious bias may be the case in some instances where the society images

and occurrences communicate in terms of body language or even choice of words. It may also be evident in classrooms where teachers praise girls for being well behaved, while boys are praised for their hard work and ideas. Some actions that are “accepted” behavior for boys, may be major disruptions for girls. Challenging gender stereotypes: a whole school approach, Optimus Education published a list of recommendations and guidelines for schools that would actively combat gender stereotypes. Their recommendation started with the curriculum. Auditing books allows teachers to maintain a balance between male and female authors, paying attention to illustrations of roles and careers in relation to genders, is vital to offer learners opportunities to see male nurses and female firefighters. They explained that even nonhuman characters need to keep the balance in terms of genders. The next guide was for teachers to consider the language they use as it had a huge effect on young children. Examples such as, dad will be picking up, my husband cooked dinner, my dad’s favorite color is pink, may create a general mood of acceptance for certain roles [4]. As children grow to observe their community, they continue to see biases in their everyday lives. Therefore, it is crucial to address it in schools and tackle the issue both through direct and indirect approaches to combat stereotypes through Education. “Teachers have a duty to have a gender-transformative approach so that we can explain to learners all of their capabilities and enable them all to fulfill their potential as people and not as boys or girls separately” Amelia Fernandez, Advisor of the Government of Navarre, and laureate of the 2019 UNESCO Prize for Girls’ and Women’s Education summarized. Alvarez Teresa, commission of citizenship and gender equality presented at the Helsinki conference “Combating gender stereotypes in the education system” the present obstacles to combating gender stereotypes in schools and proposed few guidelines to address such stereotypes through the education system and schools [1]. Social stereotypes are everywhere in the society and targeting schools alone as a means of solution may not be sufficient. The relationships that children build and maintain with their parents, relatives, neighbors, community and friends have a huge impact on what definition they build about men and women. the structural gender stereotypes envision the role of education for girls as preparing them to be caring individuals for others and proper mothers. While the same education system is planned to help boys become dominating figures, non-affective individuals and competitive elements in building self-identity. The different expectations of the same education system create an imbalance that is witnessed inside classrooms. The teachers who manage these classrooms need to be aware of these presumptions, neutralize them and move forward to rebuild new images and meanings for children. A converging education system, with trained teachers can help minimize the gap, crystallize the capabilities and opportunities of both genders and consequently, allow further integration, teaming up to solve problems, offering same experiences and subject content and methods to both genders. Alvarez offers strategies to combat gender stereotypes through education. Curriculum, including content

and knowledge, school training and professional development for teachers and all other staff, school culture and administrative leader, as well as overall community relationships. He places the highest weight on knowledge, in creative active citizenships and democracy through education. Initial training of teachers in pedagogical and scientific curriculum focusing on work and gender studies, followed by continuous training and support, making resources ready to raise teacher awareness of gender issues and allowing them to confront and speak up any issues inside their classroom as podium for learners to express, learn, grow and then move to society [1]. Teachers influence their learners as content knowledge and pedagogical means, yet their impact is much more if they deal with class interaction and issues with understanding and compassion. It is vital to shed light on the culture and environment that teachers create in classrooms. A climate that reinforces past presumptions and prevents understanding and equality or welcomes diversity and celebrates both genders. Self-aware teachers know about their own thoughts and even pre assumptions, yet seek to manage them. They enter classrooms with patience and compassion, creating stress free productive areas that motivate learners and encourage collaboration, cooperation and effective communication. Emotionally intelligent teachers spend time and effort to train learners on these social emotional skills that may account to life success. They use their both personal and professional experiences, their curricula and teaching methodologies to spread the spirit of acceptance and justice.

The future can be changed through education and if classrooms and education systems improve, then future will also be transformed and improves. Combatting social stereotypes within classrooms through teacher training and offering them resources can help create a slightly fairer future.

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